

BUXORODAGI ME'MORIY OBIDA "CHOR BAKR"

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Buxoro hududidagi me'moriy obidalaridan Chor bakr majmuasining X asrda Sumitan qishlog'iga Buxorodan Xodsharun nomli darvoza orqali o'tib borilgan. Xodsharun darvozasi XV-XVI asrlarda Talipoch ya'ni "Xon tepaligi" deb nomlangan. To'rtta buyuk avliyo Hazrat Abu Bakr Sa'd Yamaniy (vaf. 970), Hazrat Abu Bakr Homid (vaf. 937), Hazrat Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Fazl (vaf. 991), Hazrat Abu Bakr Tarxon (vaf. 945) sharofatlaridan bu mavze Chor Bakr ya'ni "To'rtta Bakr" deb atalganligi qisqacha sharhlari bilan mujassamlashtirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Chor Bakr, Sumitan G'iyos-Ul Lug'ot Abdullaxon II Yunenko, Nekropol, Narshaxiy, Varaxsha Samarqand.

Chor Bakr xalq orasida mashhur bo'lgan ushbu majmua ziyoratgohga aylangan. Joy nomi ham Chor Bakr bo'lib Buxoroning qadimiy qishloqlaridan biri sanaladi va o'z davrida Sumitan deb atalgan. "G'iyos-ul lug'ot" asarida unga "jundan mato to'quvchilar maskani" deya sharh beriladi. Chor Bakrdagi binolar XVI-XIX asrlarga mansub. Obidada 26 ta hovli, darvozaxona, peshtoqlar, madrasa, masjid-xonaqoh, hammom, dam olish hujralari, hovuz, darsxona, mustahabxonalar yaxlit bir ansanbilni tashkil etadi. Obidaning nomi ham o'sha davrlarga borib taqaladi. Majmuaning eng qadimiy qismi X asrda shakllangan bo'lib, uning nomlanishi shu yerda dafn etilgan islom olamining ko'zga ko'ringan vakllari, hadisshunos va fiqh ilmining bilimdonlari bo'lmish Chor Bakr, yani to'rtta Bakr tarixi bilan bo'g'liq.

Tadqiqotlarimiz shuni ko'rsatadiki, Chor Bakr, ya'ni to'rtta Abu Bakrlar xususida yakdil fikr mavjud emas. Biroq X asrda yashab, mazkur majmuada dafn qilingan va Buxoro xoni Abdullaxon II (XVI asr) davrida chor Bakr majmuasining qurilishiga sababchi bo'lgan dastlabki ikki Abu Bakr borasida shak-shubha yo'q. Bular Abu Bakr Sa'd Yamaniy hamda uning o'g'li Abu Bakr Ahmad ibn Sa'dlardir. Manbalarda keltirishilicha "Abu Bakr" aslida ism emas

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, balki nisba (unvon, laqab, kuniya)dir. Uning arab tilidagi tarjimasi “Baklar otasi”yoki “Bakrlar avlodi”ma’nolarini beradi. Abu Bakr Siddiqdan keyin Payg’ambarning boshqa avlodlari, jumladan, Imom Husaynning o’g’li xo’ja Abu Bakr Sa’d ham “Abu Bakr “nisbasini qabul qilgan. Chor Bakr me’moriy majmuasi Buxoro xoni shayboniy Abdullaxon II tomonidan 1559- yilda xonaqoh, masjid, madrasa va katta bog’dan iborat me’moriy majmua sifatida barpo etilgan, keyingi asrlarda yana qo’shimcha binolar qurilib, atrofi bog’larga aylantirilgan. Mazkur me’moriy majmua uchun Abdullaxon II 70 ming tilla sarflagan. Mazkur majmuada xonaqoh mavjud bo’lib, uning uch tomonida eshiklar mavjud. Bino peshtoqi 3 qavatdan iborat bo’lib, ikki hujrali, gumbazsimon peshtoqdan iborat. Xonaqohning qibla tomonida mehrob mavjud. Chor Bakr yani to’rtta Bakrlar bular kimlar Abu Bakr Sa’d, Abu Bakr Fazl, Abu Bakr Muhammad, Abu Bakr Tarxon

Abu Bakr Sa’d, Abu Bakr Axmad ibn Xoja Sa’d Yamaniy (9-asr oxiri - 971)-Buxoroda tug’ilgan. Uning otasi Xoja Sa’d Yamaniy imom Husayinning Zaynulobidin ismli o’g’lining farzandi bo’lib, u Ali ibn al-Husayn bilan birgalikda kelib ketgan (9- asrning so’ngi choragida). Narshaxiyning yozishicha Somoniylar amiri Ismoil Somoniy unga Buxoro yaqinidagi Jo’yi Mo’liyon mavzeidagi serhosil yerlarni katta qismini vaqf qilib bergan . Xoja Sa’d Buxoro atrofidagi Sumitan qishlog’ida chorbog’, bog’, sardoba, tegirmon, hovuz va boshqa binolar barpo etib, bu yerdan katta daromad olgan Abu Bakr Sa’d va uning avlodlari somoniylar davrida Buxoroda shayxulislomlik qilishgan. Abu Bakr Sad otasi vafot etgandan so’ng uning o’rniga Ismoil Somoniyning piri bo’lgan. U fiqh maktabini tashkil etib ko’plab ulamolarga ustozlik qilgan.

ABU BAKR FAZL. Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Fazl ibn Ja’far al- Buxoriy (9-asrning 2-yarmi -937?)-Imom Ja’far as-Sodiq avlodidan. Somoniylar davrida Buxoroga kelib qolgan. Uning “Musnadi Fazl” kitobi ayniqsa mashhur bo’lib bu asar bu asar Chingizxon Buxoroni bosib olganda yondirib yuborilgan.

ABU BAKR MUHAMMAD. Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Hamid (9-asrning 2-yarmi -937?)-Unga “shayx ul olam “unvoni berilgan. U Abu Bakr Fazl bilan bir yilda vafot etgan va ikkalasining ham qabrlari bir joyda yonmayon joylashgan.

ABU BAKR TARXON. Imom Abu Bakr Tarxon (9-asrning 2-yarmi - 945?)-”Kitobi Mullazoda “asarida yozilishicha ,u “Jome’va musnad” kitobini yozgan.

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Chor Bakr majmuasi bir biriga tutashib ketgan oilaviy xazira va dahmalardan iborat bo'lib, ularning old tomoni peshtoqlar va hujralar husn berib turuvchi yaxlit devor bilan o'ralgan. Chor Bakr nomi bilan mashhur bu majmua O'rta Osiyo me'morchiligining eng ajoyib namunalaridan biri hisoblanib, unda XVI-XVII asr me'morchiligining Buxoro maktabi usullari yaqqol ko'zga tashlanadi. Chor Bakr majmuasi to'g'risida tarixchi Narshaxiy "Buxoro tarixi" kitobida quyidagicha yozadi. 889-yil Ali ibn al-Husayn Buxoroga keladi. Amir Ismoil Somoniy u kishini yaxshi kutib oladi. Ali ibn al-Husayn bilan birga o'sha mashhur Chor Bakrlar ham bu quyoshli yurtga tashrif buyurib, bir umrga shu yerga qolib ketishadi. Ja'far va Aliavlodidan bo'lmish Bakrlar Buxoro shohi atrofida jiplashib, ilmu irfonning targ'ibotiga katta hissa qo'shadilar.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytish kerakki Chor Bakr majmuasi YUNESKO Umumjahon merosi obyektlari ro'yxatiga kiritilgan. Chor Bakr majmuasi 40 ga ni tashkil etadi va shundan 12ga qabristonlar mavjud ya'ni bu yerni nekropol desak bo'ladi. Nekropol so'zi grekchadan tarjima qilganda o'liklar shahri deb ataladi. Buxoro hududidagi Varaxsha hamda Samarqand hududida ham shunday joylar mavjud.

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